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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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QUALITY MANAGEMENT AS A FUNCTIONAL AND ATTRIBUTIVE CHARACTERISTIC OF MODERN MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: The objective of this study is twofold: first, to determine the methodological and practical significance of the category of "management quality" for the theory and practice of social management; and second, to reveal the conceptual understanding of this category by modern managers and the methods they employ to enhance it. The evolution of management science and practice has highlighted specific characteristics of modern management, including the imperative of continuous improvement in organisational quality, the transformation of the subject-object paradigm of managerial relations into a subject-subject paradigm, and the widespread use of project-based methods. A significant distinction of the 21st-century paradigm compared to traditional models lies not only in the expansion of classical management functions, but also in the emergence of specialised functions such as marketing, innovation management, and the implementation of product and service quality standards. Thus, quality management is recognised as both a novel function and a key attribute of contemporary management systems. The study of management quality is fundamental for advancing theory and optimising social management practice. The conceptualisation of its role, the development of theoretical constructs and models, and their empirical testing form the basis for targeted improvements in organisational management, ensuring sustainable and successful development.

Key words: management model, management quality, modern management, management paradigm, competition.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqotning maqsadi ikki yo'nalishda ko'riladi: birinchidan, "boshqaruv sifati" kategoriyasining ijtimoiy boshqaruv nazariyasi va amaliyoti uchun metodologik hamda amaliy ahamiyatini aniqlash; ikkinchidan, zamonaviy menejerlarning ushbu kategoriya haqidagi tushunchasini va uni oshirish usullarini o'rganish. Boshqaruv ilmi va amaliyotining rivojlanishi zamonaviy boshqaruvning o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini ko'rsatib berdi. Ular orasida tashkilotlarda boshqaruv sifatini uzluksiz takomillashtirish zarurati, boshqaruv munosabatlarining sub'ekt-obyekt paradigmasidan sub'ekt-sub'ekt paradigmasiga o'tishi hamda loyiha asosidagi faoliyat usullarining keng qo'llanilishi muhim o'rin tutadi. XXI-asr boshqaruv paradigmasining an'anaviy modellardan asosiy farqi nafaqat klassik boshqaruv funksiyalarining mazmunini kengaytirishda, balki marketing, innovatsion boshqaruv va mahsulot hamda xizmatlar sifat standartlarini joriy etish kabi yangi ixtisoslashgan funksiyalarning paydo bo'lishida namoyon bo'ladi. Shu bois boshqaruv sifati zamonaviy boshqaruv tizimlarining yangi funksiyasi va asosiy atributi sifatida e'tirof etiladi. Boshqaruv sifatini o'rganish nazariya taraqqiyoti va ijtimoiy boshqaruv amaliyotini optimallashtirish uchun muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Uning konseptual rolini belgilash, nazariy modellarni ishlab chiqish va ularni empirik sinovdan o'tkazish tashkilot boshqaruvini maqsadli takomillashtirish hamda barqaror rivojlanishini ta'minlash uchun asos bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: boshqaruv modeli, boshqaruv sifati, zamonaviy boshqaruv, boshqaruv paradigmasi, raqobat.

Аннотация: Цель данного исследования двоякая: во-первых, определить методологическое и практическое значение категории "качество управления" для теории и практики социального менеджмента; во-вторых, выявить концептуальное понимание этой категории современными менеджерами, а также методы, используемые ими для её совершенствования. Развитие науки и практики управления позволило выделить ряд характерных особенностей современного менеджмента, включая необходимость непрерывного повышения качества организационного управления, трансформацию парадигмы "субъект-объект" в "субъект-субъект" и широкое использование проектных методов работы. Существенным отличием парадигмы XXI века от традиционных моделей является не только расширение содержания классических функций управления, но и появление новых специализированных функций, таких как маркетинг, инновационный менеджмент и внедрение стандартов качества продукции и услуг. В результате качество управления рассматривается как новая функция и ключевая характеристика современных систем менеджмента. Изучение качества управления имеет фундаментальное значение для развития теории и оптимизации практики социального управления. Формулирование его концептуальной роли, разработка теоретических моделей и их эмпирическая апробация служат инструментальной основой для целенаправленного совершенствования управления организацией, обеспечивая её устойчивое и успешное развитие.

Ключевые слова: модель управления, качество управления, современный менеджмент, парадигма управления, конкуренция.

INTRODUCTION

Contemporary management thinking, in both its practical and research dimensions, acknowledges a fundamental difference between 21st-century management and the traditional management model that emerged at the end of the 19th century. Notwithstanding the evolving nature of contemporary management, its distinctive features are already amenable to reflection and analysis.

It is this author's opinion, based on the evidence presented, that the core attribute of the contemporary management system is the necessity of continuous improvement of its own quality. The present necessity is determined by the conditions of hypercompetition, market oversaturation, and consumer information overload, which highlight the role of high-quality goods and services. In this context, consumer choice is made in favour of the optimal price offer combined with the highest quality, which makes the latter the cornerstone of the economic entity's prosperity. Nevertheless, in contrast to the management of product quality and operational processes, which became the subject of extensive development in the 20th century, the current paradigm places emphasis on the quality of the management process itself.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The quality of management has long been recognised as a decisive factor in ensuring the efficiency and sustainability of organisations. Belenkova emphasised the socio-anthropological dimension of management, demonstrating that organisational practices are deeply influenced by the human factor within technological and production processes. Similarly, Figlin analysed the social potential of management quality, highlighting its role in strengthening efficiency, competitiveness, and the long-term development of institutions. These works show that management quality is not limited to operational effectiveness but is intrinsically connected to social and cultural dynamics.

Classical and contemporary scholars have contributed significantly to rethinking the concept of management quality. Drucker argued that the challenges of the 21st century require managers to not only administer but also to innovate, foresee, and adapt strategies to changing conditions. Mikheeva examined specific methods of assessing management quality, focusing on measurable indicators of efficiency and reputation. Later, Malenkov and Kostin provided comprehensive insights into modern management systems, identifying the expansion of managerial functions and the emergence of specialised subsystems such as crisis management and quality control.

Recent research has expanded the discourse by connecting management quality with broader socio-economic and cultural contexts. Kengesbayevich investigated the ethnocultural aspects of value orientations and their impact on managerial practices, while Poznyakov and Andreev examined the transformation of subject-object relations into more egalitarian subject-subject interactions within management. Together, these studies underline the shift from traditional hierarchical models to more flexible, innovative, and human-centred approaches, where quality management becomes both a function and an attribute of modern managerial systems.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This process is of significant importance for management theory and practice, which determines the sustained scientific interest in the issue, reflected in the works of representatives of economic science (S. V. Mikheeva, V. A. Vinokurov) and sociology (L. T. Volchkova, L. A. Figlin). The significance of management quality is pertinent to such complex characteristics of an organisation's condition as efficiency, competitiveness, business reputation, and sustainability, since it has a direct determining impact on them.

Consequently, the conceptualisation of the role of management quality, the development and empirical testing of theoretical models for improving it, are tools for targeted management improvement. The outcome of this process is a transition to a qualitatively different professional level of management – from top management to the coordinated activities of the entire team, which ultimately leads to the achievement of higher economic results by the organisation.

The following determinants can be identified that highlight the need to improve management quality:

- A) The market is characterised by oversaturation and intensified competition for consumer demand.
- B) The necessity for consumers to have access to selection criteria is predicated on the prevailing conditions of information overload with regard to manufacturers and goods. In this context, the possession of competitive advantages is predicated on factors including product/service quality, presentation quality, and a positive social image of the company.

- C) Rapid changes in socio-economic conditions necessitate that organisations be able to adapt quickly and demonstrate strategic flexibility.
- D) An increase in societal demand for self-fulfilment and the strengthening of individual consciousness, which necessitates the introduction of humanistic and personalised approaches to management that take the human factor into account.
- E) An increase in the accessibility of specialised education, literature, and research in the field of management, as well as the dissemination of training technologies, has resulted in the establishment of a substantial body of highly qualified management personnel.

It is the contention of the present study that quality management constitutes an integral basis for the implementation of other contemporary management trends, which will be analysed below ^[7].

The second fundamental characteristic of modern management is the transformation of the paradigm of managerial interaction, consisting in the transition from a subject-object model to a subject-subject model. This model is predicated on the establishment of egalitarian relationships between management and staff in the context of management processes and joint activities. Within this theoretical framework, both actors of managerial interaction act as carriers of an active, reflective principle, manifested in the ability to set goals, self-organise, and make conscious choices. It is evident that subject-subject interaction is realised in the forms of dialogue, co-management, and partnership ^[6].

The key consequences of this transformation are the subjectification of the employee's personality, the satisfaction of their higher social and existential needs, and the formation of a responsible attitude towards the results of joint activities. The following tools have been identified as effective means of implementing the proposed strategy:

- The delegation of authority and subsequent empowerment of relevant individuals or groups is of paramount importance.
- The establishment of autonomous bodies within teams is imperative for the advancement of self-governing institutions.
- The objective is to enhance the level of confidence exhibited by the management team in the professional capabilities of the personnel under their supervision.

It is important to note that in the operational activities of an organisation, both types of relationship – subject-object and subject-subject – must be in a balanced combination, but the evolutionary trend is determined by the dominant role of the latter.

It is this author's opinion that the genesis of this trend is due to a complex of socio-cultural and economic factors:

1. It is evident that there has been an increase in the overall educational level of employees.
2. This transformation of the economic structure is characterised by the predominance of intellectual labour over industrial and physical labour.
3. A change in the nature of management activity itself is becoming evident, in which the necessity and value of involving personnel in the processes of developing and implementing management decisions is becoming a key factor in organisational efficiency and innovative potential.

A further distinctive feature of contemporary management is the intensification of project activity within organisational structures, which has resulted in the establishment of a new management discipline: project management. The genesis of this trend is attributable to a complex set of macroeconomic and social processes, namely the growing individualisation of consumer demand, which has replaced the standardisation of the industrial era; the shortening of the life cycles of goods and organisations; and the deepening of the globalisation of economic relations ^[5].

A consensus has been reached in modern scientific literature regarding a number of key features of the current management paradigm.

1. The environmental determinant of management decisions and production technologies. This aspect is becoming critically important in the context of escalating global environmental challenges, making the implementation of green management an imperative for the sustainable development of society.
2. The differentiation of general management and the professionalisation of functional subsystems are two key concepts that require careful consideration. There has been a discernible trend of specialisation within the field of management, with distinct areas such as financial management, quality management, crisis

management, and PR emerging as discrete entities. Consequently, this has resulted in the emergence of a distinct class of professional managers who possess highly specialised expertise.

3. The present paper sets out to explore the creative nature of the strategic planning process. The creative aspect of management work is most evident in the development of multi-variant and scenario plans that integrate the assessment of the various consequences of decisions made. Consequently, contemporary managerial roles necessitate a multifaceted skill set, encompassing not only the formulation of operational tactics but also the development of long-term strategic direction.
4. The concept of innovation processes is characterised by two key qualities: permanence and totality. Innovation has evolved into a continuous and pervasive process that permeates all areas of an organisation's activities, thus becoming a fundamental condition for maintaining its competitiveness.
5. The process of democratisation of management is concomitant with the institutionalisation of self-management principles. This tendency is exemplified by the establishment of network teams, project groups, and the evolution of collective forms of ownership. The integration of staff within management processes has been demonstrated to engender enhanced productivity and quality of work, optimised costs, and improved overall efficiency and return on investment.
6. The management's social orientation. This phenomenon is evident in both the company's internal corporate policy and its external communications. The social image and reputation of an organisation are transformed into a critically important strategic asset, providing competitive advantages in the struggle for consumers and highly qualified personnel.

In a post-industrial society, it is important to emphasise that personal development and self-fulfilment become the dominant determinants of an individual's activities. In this regard, management is tasked with the creation of a working environment and system of opportunities that would enable staff to achieve this goal ^[3].

The following key transformations in modern management are of particular significance ^[10]:

1. The advent of information technology has precipitated a paradigm shift in the nature of work. This shift has been characterised by the intensification of information exchange and communication processes, and the concomitant minimisation of risks and uncertainty in management decision-making that are attributable to information deficits.
2. The increase in the number of management personnel is attributable to the active development of the small and medium-sized enterprise sector.
3. The adaptive nature and long-term genesis of management in a transitional economy are manifest in its flexibility, adaptability, and manoeuvrability. Concurrently, a novel management paradigm is emerging at the micro level, that is, within individual economic entities. This perspective is concurred with by a number of eminent researchers, including P. Drucker, V. A. Kostin, O. A. Belenkova, and Yu. A. Malenkov. The latter, in particular, emphasises the important characteristic of the expansion and substantive enrichment of managers' functions, as well as the emergence of new management tasks ^[1]. This phenomenon can be attributed to several factors. Firstly, the management environment is becoming increasingly complex. Secondly, there is a need to maximise the internal reserves of managers. Thirdly, there is a need to strengthen their influence on the final economic results of the organisation's activities. Finally, there is a need to raise the intellectual level and professional competence of the management team.

In this paper, Yu. A. Malenkov draws attention to a number of emergent functions of modern management. The following aspects appear to be the most pertinent from our perspective ^[8]. In the contemporary business environment, characterised by the accelerated renewal of production capacities and product lines, as well as the emergence of novel management methodologies and technologies, the imperative for continuous education and self-education among managerial personnel has become paramount.

The primary emphasis should be on enhancing competitiveness. This refers to the activities of managers aimed at increasing the competitiveness of their respective departments, with a view to taking into account benchmark indicators of similar structures in leading companies. In organisations that function effectively, competition is present not only in the external environment, but also, and primarily, in the internal environment, initiated at the level of individual workplaces. Another salient factor that merits attention is the emergence of civilised competition, predicated on the principles of open competition, comparative analysis of the performance of disparate managers, and the enhancement of their individual competitiveness ^[4].

The following is a list of the interpersonal and network communications that are to be conducted: This category encompasses information exchange processes that are conducted through both direct personal interaction and computer information networks. These processes result in a substantial reduction in time costs and

an exponential expansion of opportunities for working with large data sets. Concurrently, it appears that the final point delineates not the emergence of a novel function, but rather the acquisition of additional content for the communicative function, which was intrinsic to the traditional management system.

P. Drucker has formulated a number of relevant management tasks for the modern context ^[2]. In their structural design, he emphasises the following aspects:

- It is imperative to recognise the necessity of personal career management as an independent activity.
- It is the responsibility of the organisation to ensure the productivity of employees who are not on its staff. This suggests that the manager's competence encompasses the administration of outsourced processes, a capacity which necessitates the cultivation of novel management competencies.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Following a thorough examination of prevailing trends, it appears feasible to extrapolate the aforementioned list and identify the subsequent additional functions:

Integrated marketing management can be defined as a management process which is concerned with the identification, forecasting, and satisfaction of market needs.

The management of innovation is a key aspect of this field. In view of the characteristics delineated above, the function in question pertains to the organisation of activities that are directed towards the practical implementation of innovations. The volume of these activities is optimised to ensure the sustainable development of the organisation.

The development and implementation of quality requirements constitutes a fundamental aspect of the project. In contemporary conditions, this function is becoming pivotal, with a focus on establishing standards and implementing quality management systems for products and services.

Concurrent with the advent of novel functionalities, the conventional management functions conceptualised by A. Fayol – namely, to foresee, organise, dispose, coordinate, and control – are undergoing substantial transformation.

Planning (foresight) is evolving towards the development of a complex multi-level system of strategic and tactical, long-term and short-term plans, as well as scenario forecasts ^[4].

In the contemporary business environment, characterised by the proliferation of multifaceted organisational structures, augmented staffing levels, the prevalence of managerial roles that encompass a multitude of responsibilities, and the advancements in communication technologies, the concept of organisation is undergoing a profound transformation in its connotation ^[9].

It is becoming evident that motivation is evolving into a multifaceted instrument, functioning both as an agent of productivity enhancement and as a conduit for staff influence. This phenomenon is exemplified by the adoption of foreign motivational technologies and the development of indigenous incentive systems that incorporate coordination and control methodologies.

The concept of control has evolved beyond the confines of supervising employee activities, encompassing the monitoring of the quality of goods and services. The available tools include recommendations for improving the management system.

Consequently, the analysis indicates that quality constitutes an integral characteristic of contemporary management, permeating both its novel functions and modifying traditional ones, thereby endowing it with the characteristics of a systemic imperative.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The quality of management activities is ultimately determinative of organisational efficiency and is pivotal to the successful development of a company. In the contemporary business environment, characterised by intense market competition and the inundation of information from manufacturers to consumers, it is asserted that the enhancement of managerial quality constitutes a pivotal catalyst for the progression of management practices.

At the commencement of 2016, an empirical study was conducted employing a variety of survey methods. The objective of this study was to ascertain contemporary managers' comprehension of the concept of "management quality" and to examine the methodologies they employ to enhance it. The study was conducted by twenty experts in the field.

The study demonstrated that, while contemporary managers are progressively acknowledging the necessity to enhance management, they frequently perceive the concepts of "quality" and "efficiency" as synonymous. In this paradigm, the desired economic result is indicative of high management quality, since all transfor-

mations in the management system are ultimately aimed at achieving certain financial and economic indicators.

The aforementioned position is formulated by experts in the field as follows: The concept of quality management can be defined as the optimisation of resource potential, with the objective of achieving the lowest possible cost and highest possible efficiency.

A further group of respondents has opted to reduce quality management to conscientious task performance, focusing on human capital development.

Concurrently, a category of managers exists who reflect specifically on the quality of management as a process. The manifestation of effective leadership in such a context is characterised by several factors. Firstly, there is a need for precise communication between management and executors, ensuring clear task definition. Secondly, the distribution of responsibilities and powers must be rational. Thirdly, there is a requirement for coordinated team interaction. Finally, the establishment of a favourable socio-psychological climate within the team is paramount. The following quote is provided for illustrative purposes: *The ability to manage effectively is defined by the competent distribution of employees' potential in order to solve current organisational tasks. It is imperative to achieve a mutual understanding within the team regarding the objectives and significance of the work being undertaken. The leadership style employed is characterised by employee involvement in the decision-making process.*

Concurrently, some managers concede that they do not undertake targeted initiatives to enhance the quality of management. Instead, they limit their actions to the distribution of powers and reactive analysis of problematic situations that arise.

Conversely, alternative perspectives posit that the quality of management is influenced by a multifaceted array of factors. The development of a detailed concept, target indicators, and a business plan for each project prior to its launch; the formation of an effective team and the development of a system of individual motivation; careful regulation of all processes; continuous improvement of one's own management competence; implementation of control; conducting post-project analysis; and recognition of the team's merits. This systematic perception of management quality is characteristic of experienced managers who have received a higher education in management.

A substantial proportion of respondents subscribe to the view that effective management is contingent upon the implementation of specific mechanisms, the development of which is a resource-intensive undertaking. The scarcity of time resources, a common occurrence among small business managers in the face of a high operational workload, impedes the process of creation and implementation. This assertion is evidenced by the following statement: *"Competent management requires targeted training, but I do not have sufficient time and material resources for this."* This predicament is most pertinent to young managers who lack a pertinent education or significant management experience.

The findings of the study corroborate the hypothesis that the establishment of theoretical frameworks and practical guidelines for enhancing the quality of management practices can serve as a viable instrument, enabling managers to undertake deliberate and methodical optimisation of organisational management.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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